

FLOWER CLASSIFICATION OF CERTAIN TAXON OF *PINUS L*, *CUPRESSUS L*, *ACER L* AND *BETULA L* DEGREE OF ALLERGIC EFFECT

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Andijon shaxrida keng tarqalgan *Pinus L*, *Cupressus L*, *Acer L* va *Betula L* turkum taksonlaridan *Pallasiana Lamb*, *C.sempervirens L*, *T. americana L*, *T. cordata Mill*, *T. platyphylla Scop*, *T. tomentosa Moench*, *A. negundo L*, *B. Pendulani* biomorfologiyasi, fenologiyasi, gulchang klasfikatsiyasi va allergik ta'sir darajalari turli manbalar asosida bayon qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: allergik, fenologiya, takson, pantoporat, kolporat, saccate, inaperture, porat.

Abstract: *Pallasiana Lamb*, *C. sempervirens L*, *T. americana L*, *T. cordata Mill*, *T. platyphylla Scop*, *T. tomentosa Moench*, *A. negundo L*, *B. Pendula* biomorphology, phenology, pollen classification and allergy levels were described based on different sources.

Key words: allergic, phenology, taxon, pantoporate, colporate, saccate, inaperture, porat.

INTRODUCTION

On November 23, 2023, with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. PF-199 on measures to further increase the level of greenness in the Republic, and to ensure environmental stability through the consistent implementation of the national project "Green Space", nationwide project "Green Space" was implemented. As part of this project, it is planned to plant seedlings of trees and shrubs and increase green areas¹⁶.

Before planting and caring for trees and shrubs, it is advisable to analyze their biology, ecology, and systematics and then use them. For this, which tree can better adapt to the environment, which one emits more oxygen than itself, and which one causes allergies, all this should be studied scientifically and then put into practice.

Among the sources of tree research in Uzbekistan, there is not enough information on the morphology of tree pollens and their levels of allergic effects.

¹⁶ <https://lex.uz/docs/-6673808> Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Decision No. PF-199 of 23.11.2023.

Allergy caused by the pollen of anemophilic plants has become the focus of attention of clinicians and ecologists. Over the past decade, allergenic ragweed pollen has become a major concern. A single ragweed plant produces more than 108 pollen grains [1] and a few pollen grains are enough to sensitize humans [2].

MATERIALS AND METHOD

In this article, the botanic description and phenology of anemophilous trees was carried out using the plant identifier of Uzbekistan. The classification of pollens and their levels of allergic effects were described based on foreign methods [3, 4, 5].

RESEARCH RESULTS

Pinus L. (Pine). P. pallasiana Lamb. A tree up to 15-20 meters tall. Petals are 8-15 cm, thin, pencil-shaped, dark green, hard, with a sharp tip. The dome is large, 6-10 cm long, 4-5 cm, dome-shaped, shiny, brown-yellow. It is grown as a houseplant.

Pollen class: saccate

Phenology: V

Allergic level: **

P. Pallasiana Lamb. Appearance of flower and pollen.

Cupressus L. (Servi). C.sempervirens L. Zarafshon archasi yoki qizil archa. A tree up to 20 meters tall. The bark is reddish. The horn is thick, oval or conical. It grows on hills and mountains, stony and gravelly slopes. The fruit ripens in October-December next year.

Pollen class: inaperturate

Phenology: IV, VI

Allergic level: **

C.sempervirens L. Appearance of flower and pollen.

Tilia L (Jo'ka). T. americana L.

Pollen Class: Colporate
Phenology: VI

Allergic level: **

T. americana L. Appearance of flower and pollen.

T. cordata Mill. Yurakbarg jo'ka. A scenic tree. It blooms in June and seeds in September. The base of the leaves is heart-shaped. Leaf bands 3-6 cm. The length of the leaves is 5-8 cm, the width is 6-9 cm. The ball is 3-9 flowers. Petals are pale yellow. Branches are reddish-brown.

Pollen Class: Colporate
Phenology: VI

Allergic level: **

T. cordata Mill. Appearance of flower and pollen.

T. platyphylla Scop. Kengbargli jo'ka. A scenic tree. It blooms in June and seeds in September. Leaves 4-8 cm. The base of the leaves is heart-shaped, the leaf band is 2.5-4.5 cm. The length and width of the leaves are 6-8 cm. The top of the leaves is dark green. The bottom is blue-green, the ball consists of 8-15 flowers. The fruit is a nut, 4-8 mm. The branches are red.

Pollen Class: Colporate
Phenology: VI
Allergic level: **

T. platyphylla Scop. Appearance of flower and pollen.

T. tomentosa Moench. Tukli jo'ka. A scenic tree. It blooms in June and seeds in September. The backs of the leaves are glabrous or simply hairy. Feather is not a silver color. Leaves are 8-14 cm, round or broadly ovate, white-gray hairy. The inflorescence consists of 2-5 flowers. Petals are 1.5-2 times longer than sepals.

Pollen Class: Colporate

Phenology: VI

Allergic level: **

. *T. tomentosa* Moench. Appearance of flower and pollen.

Acer L (Zarang) A. negundo L. SHumtol zarang. The tree is up to 20 m tall. The leaves are feathery, 3-7 leaflets. The fruit is winged, 3-6 cm. Cultivated plant widespread in the republic.

Pollen Class: Colporate

Phenology: IV

Allergic level: ***

A. negundo L. Appearance of flower and pollen.

Betula L (Qayin) B. Pendula. Oq qayin. A tree with a height of 10-20 m. The bark is oozing, separable. The leaves are rhombic-ovate, hairless, with sharp edges. The flowers are unisex. Monoecious plant. Topguli-kuchala. It blooms in April and seeds in October. It grows on the banks of streams in mountainous regions, it is cultivated in city streets and avenues [6].

Pollen Class: Porate

Phenology: IV

Allergic level: **

B. pendula. L. Appearance of flower and pollen.

In conclusion, it can be said that as a result of studying the morphobiological characteristics of some tree pollens scattered in the atmosphere, the classification of pollens was clarified, according to which 5 types of colpate, 1 type of saccate, 1 type of inaperturate, and 1 type of porate were determined. Pallasiana Lamb, *C. sempervirens* L, *T. americana* L, *T. cordata* Mill, *T. platyphylla* Scop, *T. tomentosa* Moench, *B. Pendula* taxa have a medium allergenic level (**) when analyzed according to their allergenic levels. *A. negundo* L was found to have a high allergenic effect (***)).

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